

Efficacy Of Parent-Child Interaction Therapy: A Randomized Control Trial

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: September 10, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: April 12, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Parent-Child Interaction Therapy (PCIT), Regular Speech Therapy Sessions (RSTS), Behavioral Problems, Language Problems</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6450339</p>	<p><i>The present research attempts to study the efficacy of Parent-child interaction therapy (PCIT) in dealing with the behavior and language problem due to behavioral disturbances in young children more than usual treatments.</i></p> <p><i>Objective: To determine the efficacy of parent-based intervention Parent-Child Interaction Therapy (PCIT), dealing with the behavior and language problem.</i></p> <p><i>Methods The study was done on a sample of 50 children ages 3 to 7year. Analysis was done by using T-test.</i></p> <p><i>Results: Result shows the clear cut difference between both of the techniques efficacy. PCIT scores are significantly higher than regular speech therapy sessions (RSTS). This clearly depicts the efficacy of PCIT.</i></p>

Introduction

Parent-Child Interaction Therapy (PCIT) is a simple and systematic technique that works together with parents and children. It is an evidence based program. This program mainly aimed to improve parent-child relationships as well as child behavior. In this program Parents learn specific skills to increase positive behavior they mainly want to promote. Parent-Child Interaction therapy (PCIT) is basically behaviour therapy. It improves the parent-child relationship by converting negative interaction into positive one (Barlow & Brown, 2000). It has been developed by Sheila Eyeberg. It is an empirically-supported treatment program for young children mainly with emotional and behavioral disorders. PCIT always emphasis on the quality of the parent-child relationship. It also helps to change parent-child relations patterns (Chase, 2005; Kigin, & McNeil, 1995).

Uniqueness of PCIT lies in teaching and training parents to develop constructive parenting skills. Unlike most therapies PCIT improve parenting skills by practicing with immediate therapist. PCIT is a weekly program. It generally has a session which is about 60 min and sessions continue a period of 12weeks to 20 weeks. It has training session and subsequent session. Training or teaching session consists of different techniques like introduction, modeling, and role-playing of very specific skills. Review of home practice and live coaching of parentchild interactions are in succeeding (subsequent) session. Instructions given through a one-way mirror and an audio transmitter worn in the parent's ear (a "bug-in-the-ear")(Eyberg et al., 1995; McNeil et al., 2001).

From therapist who sits in the corner of the room in a way that child isn't able to see therapist but therapist is able to guide the parents. Home sessions are important part of the programme and it takes only 5 to 15min.

PCIT has two phases: the *Child-Directed Interaction or relationship enhancement* and *ParentDirected Interaction or Discipline and Compliance* phases. Teaching phase is a beginning step with parents for the introduction of the skills that will be the center of that phase and this is without the child. Remaining sessions include the child and entail live practice with both (parent and child) PCIT has two stages, relationship development and discipline training. In other words child directed or parent-directed interaction. with pre-treatment, mid-treatment, post-treatment assessment (Goldfine et al., 2008).

Positive attention is given by the parents to the suitable child behavior whereas they use diverse attention to reduce minor negative behaviors. Parental teaching also include a time-out technique to use when their child disobey or display other rule-breaking behaviors. Parents training to use during Special Time is restricted use of skills. Although the skills vary from person to person, it is generally either "DRIP" or "PRIDE." Means praise, reflection, imitation, description and enthusiasm. During whole process Child's appropriate behavior is being praised by the parents—for example telling them, "good job cleaning up mess"—so parent promote the wanted

behavior and make the child feel good. Parents repeat and build upon child communication by listen carefully. Parental encouragement is needed to improving communication.

Parents repeat child acts for approval of needed behavior and help to teach them to learn how to play with others. Parents description of the child's act (e.g. "You're brushing your teeth") to reveal interest and build vocabulary. They being Parents are passionate and their excitement about what the child is doing natural.

Parent's mainly trained to appreciate wanted behaviors i.e. greeting. They ignore unwanted or frustrating behavior which is problematic. In addition, avoidance of criticisms and negative words—such as "no," "don't," "stop," or "quit"—and as an alternative concentration on positive directions is also taught to them. Along with the trained sessions, homework sessions to practice newly acquired skills with their child are also needed.

Most therapists currently use term PRIDE instead of DRIP. Here "E" supports the value and importance of positive parenting commitment. As PCIT is evidence based and progressively encouraging treatment programs (Eyberg, Boggs, & Algina, 1995).

So the present study also aiming to prove that how much PCIT is effective in handling behavioral and language problems in young children. This study is also trying to prove the cost effectiveness of PCIT.

PCIT is new embryonic concept in the field of speech pathology in Pakistan. Current study will not only understand the benefits of PCIT rather provide an alternate way to help those parents who are not able to bring their children for the regular speech and language therapy.

Aims and Objectives:

The objective of this study is to determine the efficacy of parent-based intervention in Pakistan. Parent-Child Interaction Therapy PCIT in treating the behavior problem and language problem due to behavioral disturbances in young children more than usual treatment.

Literature Review

Sheila Eyeberg developed Parent-Child Interaction Therapy (PCIT) in the 1970s. It is basically for children between 2 to 7yrs and was with disruptive behavior disorders.

Since then PCIT is commonly used, evidence-based treatment.

PCIT includes 2 phases. Basically it usually needs up to 15 sessions. Goals of the first phase are to improve the quality parent-child relationship. It also works for intensifying attention with reinforcement for positive child behavior. Child-Directed Interaction (CDI) is first phase of PCIT (Solomon et al., 2008). In the CDI, parents learn how to behave and react in dyadic play. It provide positive attention combined with active ignoring of minor misbehavior (Eyberg et al., 2001). Parents are taught to apply the PRIDE skills—P-Praise, R-Reflection, I-Imitation, D-Description, and E-Enthusiasm behaviours which are positive and appropriate enhanced through these skills. Parents also get skilled to avoid unwanted behavior like commands, inquiring and negative behaviors. The consequent phase CDI actually makes bases for effective discipline training i.e. Parent-Directed Interaction (PDI) (McNeil & Hembree-Kigin., 2010). In this stage parents learn to direct their child's activity both in play situations as well as in real life conditions where obedience is required from their child. They learn to give instructions. They also get aware with consequences. Like praise a timeout for compliance and non compliance (Harrison-Morehouse., 2016).

Salient characteristic of PCIT is that it is very intense in delivery. Basically PCIT deals with direct coaching about parent and child interactions. So this live coaching of the parental skills during parent and child interactions is the mark of PCIT. Teaching session is the key session with parents or care givers for both the phases, to teach and introduce principles and skills to the parents. The consequent session is also known as coaching sessions basically for reviewing homework. After reviewing homework therapists coach each parent and child dyad one by one. Coaching is done via a wireless earphone in clinic-based PCIT mainly through a one-way mirror (Funderburk & Eyberg, 2011). The child and parent interact in the therapy room and being coached by therapist from an adjacent room behind. Sometimes the therapist remains in the same room but at a place invisible b for the child. (McNeil & Hembree-Kigin., 2010).

Parental training is the key factor that can enhance benefits of the PCIT. This training mainly includes teaching parents to use play skills. There are abundant studies indicating PCIT effectiveness which includes open trials and randomized controlled trials.

Schumans and his research fellows did a randomized trial and his short-term report indicates effectiveness of Parent-Child interaction Therapy (PCIT).

The content and process of PCIT was reported satisfactory by all families who received treatment. Data showed that during preliminary 4-month follow-up all measures noted through self report indicate maintenance in gain.

Timmer and his fellows in 2010 researched on 62 children (ages 2 to 7) exposed to domestic violence. Decrease in disruptive behavior, anxiety and depression in children undergoing PCIT noted. Significant improvement in overall psychological functioning was reported by mothers participating in PCIT.

An open trial was done Sternberg and his research fellows in 2006 on a sample of 133 parent-child dyads. Children who were physically abused, neglected and/or children of drug-induced parents were participated in this research. Their ages range from 2 to 8. All of them who were in PCIT reported significant decreases in disruptive behavior, depression, anxiety and other symptoms (Urquiza, 2010).

In another trial done by Timmer and his fellows with 62 children. Their ages were 2 to 7 and they were exposed to domestic violence. Mothers of this study also reported considerable improvement in overall psychological functioning and children participating in PCIT also exhibit decrease in disruptive behavior and associated symptoms (Timmer, Ware, Urquiza, & Zebell, 2010).

The efficacy of PCIT in young children physically abused was studied in three randomized controlled trials (Chaffin et al., 2010; Chaffin, 2004; Thomas & Zimme, 2011). Out of 110 parents those with confirmed new physical abuse report (child 4 to 12 years of age) were randomly assigned 49 to PCIT. Individualized enhanced services and PCIT, or a standard community-based parenting group were other groups of the study (Chaffin, 2004). Community group members (parents) showed no change from baseline. Significant decrease in negative parent and child interactions was shown by the Parents assigned to PCIT or PCIT plus enhanced services. After 850 days at a median follow up 19% of PCIT group parents had a re-report for physical abuse as compared to 49% assigned to the standard community parenting group. No improvement in the efficacy additional enhanced services group is reported.

In a randomized controlled trial for studying the efficacy of PCIT (Kohlhoff et al., 2020). Sample of 192 parents with a 6 prior maltreatment reports were included and at beginning of study children of about 76% of the parents were (ages 2 through 12) in foster care (Chaffin et al., 2010). PCIT dyads were returned home. They returned home sooner than those assigned to usual treatment. (Over a median follow-up of 904 days) (Chaffin et al., 2010).

In an Australian study 150 mothers who maltreated their children along with those at high risk of it were randomly assigned to PCIT as well as to a wait-list control group (Owen, et al., (2018). PCIT receiving Parent-child dyads showed marked improvement as compared to the control group. Mothers who were in PCIT dyads reported considerable decrease in parental stress. Disruptive behavior markedly decreases for the children of PCIT. Observations indicate suspected maltreatment rate reduction (17% vs. 43%) in families who completed PCIT (Eyberg, 2008).

In another open trial of children ages 2 to 8 PCIT proves significant decreases in depression, disruptive behavior and anxiety. Noticeable decreases in parenting stress in the foster parents was noted (Timmer, Urquiza, & Zebell, 2006; Thomas, & Gembeck, 2011).

In 2015 a research was done by Allen and Marshall using PCIT in school-going children with specific language impairment. Language gains were shown by all the kids in the treated group as compared to the control group. Three of the five communication parameters: verbal initiation, MLU (mean length of utterance) and the proportion of child-to-parent utterances were positively affected by PCIT. However minor effect on verbal responses.

Sharon K. Millard was one who utilizes PCIT to deal with young children who stutter. He finds pre and post stuttering frequency data indicates marked difference. Stuttering reduction in 6 children was reported by both parents. It is (PCIT) is cost effective which is indicated by clinically significant enhancement on the CBCL (reduction ranging from 17–61%) (Eyberg, Boggs, & Algina, 1995).

If we consider the local literature than it is really unfortunate that no research is available in Pakistan relating this topic. This is going to be the first ever study in Pakistan. In this particular study efficacy of PCIT is going to be measured by comparing it with regular speech and language therapy.

Material and Methods

Operational Definitions:

Behavioral problems:

Behavior disorders (e.g. attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder, oppositional defiant disorder, conduct disorder) are among the most common reasons children are referred for mental health services (Kazdin, Mazurick, & Siegel, 1994; Reid, 1930). So, problem that may manifest disturbances in Emotions (anxiety or depression) Behavior (aggression) Physical function (psychogenic disorders), Mental performance (problems at school).

Language problems:

Language disorders are of two types receptive and expressive. Receptive (e.g. listening) language disorders involve problems in understanding language.

Expressive (e.g. Speaking) language disorders involves problems in using language (Owens, 1996)

In Language disorders child has trouble understanding what others say or difficulty sharing her thoughts.

PCIT Intervention:

PCIT is a treatment strategy that nurtures parent-child relationship and teaches effective parenting strategies to decrease child non-compliance behavior (BodifordMcNeil & Hembree-Kigin, 2010). PCIT has its roots in social learning, and attachment theories and proceeds along two successive phases: Child-Directed Interaction (CDI) and Parent-Directed Interaction (PDI).

PROCEDURE

At CDI stage skills that must be put into practice, through the PRIDE (Praise, Reflect, Imitate, Describe and Enthusiasm).

Steps For Teaching CDI Skills

1. Review the homework tasks
2. Describe the objectives of CDI
3. Discuss the five minutes of daily practice at home
4. Explain and present models of the behaviours to be avoided
5. Explain and present models of the skills to be carried out
6. Discuss the use of strategic attention
7. Discuss the use of selective ignoring
8. Model all of the combined skills
9. Train the parents through role-play
10. Discuss the logic of play therapy at home
11. Assign new homework activities

Steps for Teaching PDI Skills

1. Explain the use of the obedience exercises
2. Discuss how to give effective instructions
3. Determine when the child obeys
4. Discuss the consequences of obedience
5. Discuss the consequences of disobedience
6. Explain how an effective time-out is carried out
7. Train parents in discipline skills

SESSIONS

Treatment procedure constitute of maximum 24 sessions. Duration of each session should be 60-90 minutes. In the present study 50 children were called at Fauji Foundation Hospital on given date. They are then divided in to two groups with 25 children each. Grouping was basically done to divide the children according to their parent's availability. Those who came from distant area are included in PCIT where as other for regular speech and language therapy. Parental consent for the study was already taken.

Study Design:

The research design of this study was Randomized Control Trial (RCT).

Main outcome measures:

Measures

Independent Measures:

Parent child interaction therapy (PCIT) and regular speech therapy session (RSTS)

Dependent Measures:

Child's behavior and language learning ability, Parent child bonding and stress management parent.

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Research model

Pre-Treatment Protocol**Post-Treatment Protocol
INTERVENTION****Hypothesis**

H0: PCIT has no effect on child's behavioral problems and language learning ability.

H1: PCIT is effective in treating child's behavioral problems and language learning ability.

Method.

Participants will be referred to the speech therapy department and will be contacted on the telephone, screened, interviewed and those who fulfill inclusion criteria will be included. Participants will be informed about the study and consent will be obtained and at the same time ECBI will be administered. If the ECBI Intensity score will be in the range, the family will complete the remaining assessment for the pre-treatment assessment. Throughout the treatment parents will complete ECBI at the beginning of each session, at the mid treatment and at the end of each session.

Post treatment will be conducted one week following the final parent directed interaction session using the same measures.

Tools and instruments for assessment

- Eyeberg child behavior inventory (ECBI)
- Child Behavior Checklist (CBCL)

Setting:

After seeking permission from hospital and securing consent from parent data will be collected from Speech and language therapy department of FFH.

Study Design:

The research design of this study would be Randomized Control Trial (RCT).

Sample size: will be calculated with sample calculator **Sampling technique:** probability sampling

Data Collection Procedure

The study was initiated after ethical approval from advanced study & research committee (ASRC). Confidentiality of participant's data will be maintained throughout the research. Informed consent will be obtained from parents and verbal assents from children prior to the participation in the study.

Throughout treatment parents completed an ECBI at the beginning of each session to determine rate of behavior improvement throughout treatment.

Selection criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

Inclusion Criteria for children:

- Participants of the study age between 3 to 7 years however both the genders are included
- Referred cases for language delay, behavioral or attention/hyperactive problems □ Parental consent to the study

Inclusion Criteria for Parents:

- Biological Parents
- Minimum education: high school
- Willing to participate

Exclusion Criteria:

Exclusion Criteria for children:

- Mental retardation or pervasive developmental disorder in the child.
- Should not be under any other kind of the therapeutic intervention .

Exclusion Criteria for Parents:

- Psychosis or serious drug abuse in parents
- Lack of sufficient proficiency in parents to fill in the questionnaires.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The purpose of the study was to determine the efficacy of parent child interaction therapy (PCIT) in comparison to the regular speech therapy sessions (RSTS). Our results indicate PCIT has positive effects on the disruptive behaviour of Pakistani children's. After the statistical analysis of both of the techniques it was noted that there is a clear cut difference between both of the techniques efficacy. The score of PCIT is significantly higher than RSTS. This clearly depicts the efficacy of PCIT. This finding proved the hypothesis that PCIT is more effective in treating behavior and language problems.

This study also proves that PCIT is really effective in treating behavioral problems like spitting, shouting, crying, temper tantrums etc. it is mainly because PCIT helps parents to form positive bonding with their children and it also taught the parents to use differential reinforcement for the different behaviors of the children. (Foote, Eyeberg and Schuhmann, 1998; Sanders et al., 2003). Significant noticeable reduction in the behavioural problems of children is reported. Therefore, after treatment almost all children behaviour fall in the range of normal functioning. The results prove PCIT a sufficient intervention strategy for reducing child behavioural problems. In this particular study 10 different attributes of behaviour and language issues were taken into account. These attributes were measured before and after treatment. Results indicate efficacy of PCIT very clearly. Attention span, Eye contact, Pointing, Gestures, Command Following, Understanding of ICW, Duration of interaction (sitting behaviour) are taken as the non-verbal expression of behaviour whereas anger displacement (aggression and temper tantrum) verbal expression of the behaviour. For assessment of language short phrase and intelligibility were taken into account.

Attention spans of pre and post interventions are compared for both PCIT and RSTS. It is very clear from findings that attention span improves in both the cases but in case of PCIT attention span mostly reached the normal limit.

It is very clear from table that pointing on command (ICW) and gestural expression also improves accordingly. In PCIT it improves up to 100% in some of the cases however usually

PCIT improvement ranges from 70% to 100% with most of the cases in the range of 80% to 100% i.e. excellent response to intervention on the other hand in RSTS improvement ranges from 50 to 90% but in most of the cases improvement fall in the range of 50% to 70% i.e. satisfactory to good response to the intervention. Last attribute of the non-verbal behavior duration of time improves markedly in PCIT than in RSTS it is very clear from the graph.

In the study anger displacement (aggression, temper tantrum) short phrase making and intelligibility were the attributes that used for verbal expression. It is well indicated from the graph that in case of PCIT all these attributes improved and progress markedly as compare to the RSTS.

Descriptive analysis Table 1:

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std .Devision
Demo-Age	50	3	7	5.5	10.644

Table 2:

Gender wise frequency analysis for children group 1

	Frequency	Percentage
Female	8	32.0
Male	17	68.0
Total	25	100.0

Table 2.1 Gender wise frequency analysis for children group 2

	Frequency	Percentage
Female	12	48.0
Male	13	52.0
Total	25	100

Reliability analysis**Table 3**

Crobach's alpha coefficient, item- total correlation and total number of items in each variable

Variable	No. of items	Crobach's Alpha
Child behavior	12	0.896
Language learning ability	36	0.812

Table 4

Comparison of language and behavior variable before and after intervention

Sample t-test analysis

Variable	t-statics	P-Value
Attention span	2.19	0.04
Eye contact	5.07	0.000
Pointing	4.0	0.001
Command following	4.79	0.000
Understanding of ICW	2.95	0.010
Duration on interaction	5.70	0.000
Anger Displacement	3.14	0.006
Phrase making	4.79	0.000
Intelligibility	2.21	0.04

PCIT is statically more significant than the controlled group as shown by results

- As P-value of attention span(0.04), eye contact(0.002), pointing(0.001), gestures(0.000), command following(0.000), understanding of ICW(0.000), duration of interaction(0.010), anger-displacement(0.006), short phrases(0.000) and intelligibility(0.04) are significant then the values of control group which are attention span(0.023), eye contact(0.032), pointing(0.043),gestures(0.035), command following(0.022), understanding of ICW(0.0075), duration of interaction(0.083), anger displacement(0.082), short phrases(0.0005) and intelligibility(0.093) .
- So the p value is significant that indicates the rejection of Null hypothesis and acceptance of Alternate hypothesis.

Limitations

This study has some limitations. Sample size was very small. Generalization is lacking. Variables such as gender, socio economic status , parental stress, children parental bond were not taken into account so there is need of study considering all these variables too.

The finding of the study although are very significant from academic point of view and is also very helpful in forming base for further studies in the field of speech and language pathology.

While PCIT is an effective management strategy in dealing with certain types of problems but limitations are there. PCIT may not be appropriate for different kind of population's e.g. less interactive parents of very young children (less than 2½ years old), Parents with serious mental health problems ie. auditory or visual hallucinations or delusions. Those who are hearing impaired and couldn't use the ear bug device. Those parents who have significant language problems i.e. receptive or expressive. Parents engaging in sadistic physical abuse or sexually abusive parents.

So parent child therapy is an interactive and innovative strategy. It's very beneficial for problematic children (ages 2½ to 8).

Recommendations

As PCIT has so many advantages so it is recommended that this study should be repeated in the future by taking in accounts all the remaining variables like socio economic status, parental education etc. study should also be repeated by taking in account population of different area so result obtained can be generalized with more accuracy. In the study anger displacement (aggression, temper tantrum) short phrase making and intelligibility were the attributes that used for verbal expression.

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